

The Reaction between Molybdic Acid and Diphenylcarbazone

Anil Paigankar and B. C. Haldar

Spectrophotometric studies by Job's continued variation method indicates that a compound of composition $\text{MoO}_2(\text{DPO})_2$, with an absorption maxima at $540\text{m}\mu$, is formed in 0.1*N*-HCl and 89% by volume of acetone. The value of the constant *K* is found to be $1.5 \pm 0.5 \times 10^7$ at $30^\circ \pm 1^\circ$. The solid compound $[\text{MoO}_2(\text{DPO})_2]^\circ$ is found to be diamagnetic and behaves like a non-electrolyte. Intense absorption maxima of the compound in benzene (ϵ_n at $540\text{m}\mu = 20,600\text{ mol}^{-1}\text{ cm}^{-1}$) and in acetone-hydrochloric acid solution (ϵ_n at $540\text{m}\mu = 6824\text{ mol}^{-1}\text{ cm}^{-1}$) are due to charge-transfer transitions.

The development of an intense violet colour¹ on the interaction of molybdenum (VI) and diphenylcarbazone has been utilised for the detection of molybdenum, but this reaction has not yet been investigated. An attempt has been made in this communication to study the physico-chemical aspects of this reaction.

EXPERIMENTAL

All the reagents used were of A.R quality. Diphenylcarbazone was prepared by oxidation of diphenylcarbazide according to Slotta and Jakobi² and purified by the method of Krumholz and Krumholz³, m.p. 127° . The purity of diphenylcarbazone was found to be 99.9% by the method of Ghosh and Ray⁴, using potentiometric end point.

A.R. quality acetone was further purified by distilling it over anhydrous potassium carbonate. A.R. HCl, free of any reducing material, was standardised against a standard solution of borax, using methyl red as an indicator⁵.

Spectrophotometric measurements were taken on a Unicam SP 500, No. 23481 spectrophotometer. Glass cells of 1 cm optical path were employed.

The stock solution of molybdic acid was prepared by dissolving a known weight of A.R. molybdic acid in HCl of known strength and it was checked by lead molybdate method⁶. Dilute solutions of molybdic acid in 0.1*N*-HCl and 89% by volume of acetone were prepared by diluting the stock solution with proper solvents.

A known weight of purified diphenylcarbazone was dissolved in a known volume of acetone, dried over anhydrous potassium carbonate. The strength of the stock solution was checked by Ghosh and Ray's method⁴. *M*/500, *M*/1500, and *M*/2000 diphenylcarbazone solutions in 0.1*N*-HCl and 89% acetone (v/v) were prepared by diluting the stock solutions with proper solvents.

All the solutions were clear and free of any precipitate or colloidal particles. Several solutions of molybdic acid (1 to 17 ml) were taken in different standard flasks and kept in ice-bath for about $\frac{1}{2}$ hr. Diphenylcarbazone solutions of same strength were next added from a burette to molybdic acid solutions, keeping the total volume 18ml. The violet

1. Krumholz and Honel, *Mikrochim. Acta*, 1937, 2, 177.

2. *Z. anal. Chem.*, 1929, 77, 344.

3. *Monatsh.*, 1937, 70, 431.

4. *This Journal*, 1960, 37, 650.

5. Vogel, "Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", 3rd ed., p. 238.

6. Scott, "Quantitative Analysis", Vol. I, 5th ed., p. 599.

colour became stable after 12 hr. and remained so for at least another 48 hr. Absorption measurements were taken at 520, 540, and 600 m μ after 12 hr. from the time of mixing.

Similar solutions of diphenylcarbazone in acetone were prepared by mixing diphenylcarbazone and HCl solvent instead of molybdic acid, keeping the total volume at 18.0 ml, and optical densities of such solutions were measured. The difference between the optical density of the mixture and the corresponding diphenylcarbazone solution was plotted against the volume of molybdic acid.

Molybdenum-diphenylcarbazone Complex.—Pure diphenylcarbazone (ca. 1.01 g.) in 70 ml of acetone was slowly added with continuous stirring to cooled (ca. 5°) 10*N*-HCl (20 ml) containing 0.4777 g. of molybdenum trioxide. The mixture after diluting with water (200 ml) and keeping for 24 hr. was filtered. The separated solid was washed repeatedly with water till free of molybdate and chloride, dried over H₂SO₄ (conc.), and dissolved in benzene. The solution was filtered to remove insoluble residue, if any. A dark chocolate solid was obtained by evaporating the benzene solution at the room temperature.

Molybdenum in the compound was estimated as lead molybdate after decomposing it with HNO₃ (conc.). The amount of diphenylcarbazone present in the complex was determined by the method of Ghosh and Ray⁴. [Found: Mo, 15.75; C, 52.00; N, 18.30; H, 3.80; O (by diff.), 10.15. Calc. : Mo, 15.83; C, 51.47; N, 18.49; H, 3.53; O, 10.63%].

A conventional freezing point apparatus was used to determine the molecular weight of the compound by cryoscopic method in benzene. Magnetic susceptibility was measured by Gouy's method.

TABLE I

Extinction coefficient of the complex.

0.00144*M*, 0.0006667*M*, and 0.0005*M* solutions of the reactants were used.

Wave length.	Extinction coefficient (in g. mol ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹)		Mean.
	Hagenmuller.	Schaepfi and Tradwell.	
520 m μ	5772	5848	5766
540	6282	6229	6256
600	2148	2150	2148

TABLE II

Determination of K.

H ₂ MoO ₄ .	HDPO.	Complex.	K × 10 ⁻⁷ .
	Wave length : 520 m μ .		
9.333 × 10 ⁻³	4.167 × 10 ⁻⁴	4.019 × 10 ⁻³	1.423
3.600 × 10 ⁻⁴	1.080 × 10 ⁻³	2.883 × 10 ⁻⁴	1.510
	Wave length : 540 m μ .		
3.200 × 10 ⁻⁴	1.120 × 10 ⁻³	2.870 × 10 ⁻⁴	1.419
6.400 × 10 ⁻⁴	8.000 × 10 ⁻⁴	2.870 × 10 ⁻⁴	1.596
	Wave length : 600 m μ .		
8.333 × 10 ⁻³	4.167 × 10 ⁻⁴	4.883 × 10 ⁻³	1.895
2.592 × 10 ⁻⁴	4.074 × 10 ⁻⁴	1.001 × 10 ⁻³	1.466

N. B. concentrations expressed in g. mol./litre.

TABLE III

Properties of the compound $[\text{MoO}_4(\text{DPO})_2]^\circ$

1. Solubility in benzene at $35^\circ \pm 0.1^\circ$: 16.04 g./litre
2. M.W. found : 597.0; calc. 606.1
3. Magnetic property: Diamagnetic.
4. Absorption maxima: 530m μ (acetone); 540m μ (benzene).

DISCUSSION

The spectral curves of molybdic acid and diphenylcarbazone, taken in the molar ratio of 1:1, 1:2, and 1:3 (Fig. 1) in 0.1 *N*-HCl and acetone (89%, v/v), show only one peak at 540 m μ , clearly revealing the formation of one complex in the solution⁷. Concentrations of both HCl and acetone have pronounced effect on the violet colour. The colour increases three and half times by changing the concentration of acetone from 33 to 89.1% (v/v).

FIG. 1. Spectral curves.

Molybdic acid conc. = $2.222 \times 10^{-4} M$.
 HDPO conc. in 1-3 are respectively
 2.222 , 4.444 , and $6.666 \times 10^{-4} M$.

With equimolecular solutions of molybdic acid and diphenylcarbazone, the curves (Fig. 2-3) obtained by Job's method⁸ indicate only one peak at the ratio of molybdic acid to diphenylcarbazone as 1 : 2. The position of the peak is independent of the concentra-

7. Vosburgh and Cooper, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.* 1941, 63, 437.

8. *Ann. chim.*, 1928, x, 9, 113.

tion of the reactants and the wave length of the light used. The reaction between molybdic acid and diphenylcarbazone may thus be represented as

where HDPO represents a molecule of diphenylcarbazone and DPO represents diphenylcarbazone less one hydrogen atom.

At constant H^+ -ion concentrations, the following relation holds good, provided that the ionic strength of the solution is kept constant.

$$K = \frac{\text{Complex formed}}{(\text{free molybdic acid}) (\text{free diphenylcarbazone})^2} \quad \dots (2)$$

FIG. 2. Job's curve.

- Curve 1: Conc. of H_2MoO_4 and $\text{HDPO} = 0.00144 M$ (both).
 Curve 2: Conc. of HDPO and $\text{H}_2\text{MoO}_4 = 0.000667 M$ (both).
 Curve 3: H_2MoO_4 and $\text{HDPO} = 0.0005 M$ (both).
 All in 0.1 N -HCl and 89% acetone.

9. *Compt. rend.*, 1950, 230, 219D; *Ann. chim.*, 1951, 6, 5.
 10. *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1948, 31, 577.

FIG. 3. Job's method of continued variation with molybdic acid and diphenylcarbazone (both 0.0005M).

Wave length in curve 1=520mμ and in curve 2=600 mμ.

The spectral curve of the solution of the complex in 0.1N-HCl and 89% acetone is found to be identical with that of the solution prepared by mixing molybdic acid and diphenylcarbazone in the same solvent mixture. The extinction coefficient of the complex has been calculated from the absorption data taken with solutions of the solid complex in the same solvent mixture and using the value of $K = 1.5 \pm 0.5 \times 10^7$. The values of the extinction coefficient at 520 mμ, 540 mμ, and 600 mμ are 6284, 6824, and 2238 mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹ respectively, which are within 8% of the values obtained by Hagenmuller's and Schaeppi and Treadwell's methods. The optical density of the complex in acetone is not affected by lithium chloride, indicating that chloride ion does not participate in the reaction. Thus it may be concluded that the same coloured species is present in 0.1N-HCl and 89% acetone solution whether it is formed by the reaction between molybdic acid and diphenylcarbazone or by the dissociation of the solid complex $[\text{MoO}_2 (\text{DPO})_2]^0$.

The structure of the complex may be written as :

FIG. 4. Spectral curves of $\text{MoO}_3(\text{DPO})_2$ in diff. solvents.
 1. $2.64 \times 10^{-5} M$ compound in benzene.
 2. $2.409 \times 10^{-4} M$,, in 01.N-HCl+89% acetone.
 3. $1.0 \times 10^{-4} M$,, in acetone

The spectra of the compound in benzene and acetone (Fig. 4) show intense absorption maxima at $540 \text{ m}\mu$ and $530 \text{ m}\mu$ respectively, which are due to charge-transfer transitions. The molar extinction coefficient of the complex in benzene at $540 \text{ m}\mu$ is found to be $20,660 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$.